

D7.4: The BEYOND Policy Recommendations on Institutional Research Ethics and Research Integrity Culture

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BEYOND Consortium

	ROLE	NAME	Acronym	Country
1.	Coordinator	University of Oslo	UiO	Norway
2.	Partner	European Network of Research Ethics Committees	EUREC	Belgium
3.	Partner	High Council For The Evaluation of Research and Higher Education	HCERES	France
4.	Partner	French Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment	INRAE	France
5.	Partner	Oslo Metropolitan University	OsloMet	Norway
6.	Partner	Eurosis Federation of Finnish Learned Societies	TSV	Finland
7.	Partner	University of Central Lancashire-Cyprus	UCLanCY	Cyprus
8.	Partner	University of Helsinki	UH	Finland
9.	Partner	University of Humanistic Studies	UHS	The Netherlands
10.	Partner	University of Latvia	UL	Latvia
11.	Partner	University of Tartu	UTARTU	Estonia
12.	Partner	Stichting VUMC / The Embassy of Good Science	VUMC	The Netherlands
13.	AP	Trilateral Research LTD	TRI	UK
14.	AP	Heriot-Watt University	HWU	SCT

The BEYOND policy recommendations on fostering responsible research cultures

Introduction

This Policy Brief is addressed to policymakers, organisational leaders, and research ethics and research integrity (RE/RI) bodies. It recognises the role of leadership and organisational culture in fostering RE/RI but also addresses the broader research ecosystem and its national and international regulators, including those responsible for performance evaluation and researcher assessment. A culture of integrity must be supported, and this can be achieved through a proactive approach to RE/RI that involves all actors across the research ecosystem.

The BEYOND project emphasises that RI is a shared responsibility and the importance of the research environment in sustaining RI. In this context, fostering responsible research cultures requires attention to the complexity of organisational culture and leadership, the recognition of the importance of prevention and proactive measures to support RI, the engagement of stakeholders across the research ecosystem, and the acknowledgement of the value of diversity and accessibility in strengthening integrity.

Engagement across the research ecosystem involves all stakeholders in research communities at national and international levels, including research-performing organisation (RPOs) and other bodies, such as research-funding organisations (RFOs). The BEYOND policy recommendations support responsible institutional cultures for research ethics and integrity. An open research culture is one in which trust is built through transparent discussion of mistakes and dilemmas, support for skills and values development, and identification of training needs.

Recommendations

Based on these principles and the evidence presented below, BEYOND recommends:

1. *Promote quality and integrity as indicators in institutional recognition systems:* RPO's must be recognised for their efforts to proactively foster and promote a responsible research culture, for example, through university rankings and performance indicators used by national ministries. Key performance indicators (KPIs) should include measures of proactive efforts to maintain integrity and to create supportive, psychologically safe research environments in which concerns and dilemmas can be raised without fear of retaliation.
2. *Prioritize proactive measures:* There must be recognition of time, personnel, targeted funding, and other resources needed to sustain a proactive approach to RE/RI. A proactive RE/RI approach requires investment, not only recognition, including dedicated time and space for ongoing dialogue about RE/RI dilemmas, reflexive practice, and

collective learning, as well as alignment of workload planning with responsible research practices.

3. *Value integrity-promoting work:* Mentoring roles and participation in committees that promote RE/RI must be recognised as academically meritorious activities, alongside currently valued tasks such as obtaining research funding, producing research outputs, supervision, and teaching. Furthermore, this recognition should also explicitly include the often invisible emotional and care work involved in supporting colleagues, discussing ethical dilemmas, and maintaining a fair and respectful research environment, especially for those in more vulnerable positions.
4. *Ensure responsible engagement with RI processes:* Research integrity-related structures must not be used to handle normal scientific disagreements or personal conflicts, as this undermines and erodes the RI infrastructure. RPOs must be vigilant in proactively supporting the appropriate use of RE/RI mechanisms and in preventing their misuse, all the time ensuring that all researchers, including and especially those in precarious or marginalized positions, are protected against the strategic misuse of RI procedures.
5. *Institutionalize a culture of integrity and support:* build a culture of integrity, safeguard credibility, and ensure trust by developing RE/RI leadership competencies across all levels of research governance and practice. These competencies should be embedded in the training of early-career researchers and all relevant stakeholders, and should include the ability to foster inclusive, non-punitive, and caring research environments that support well-being, openness to mistakes, and fair treatment for all members of the research community.

Evidence and background information to support the recommendations

1. *Performance indicators* . Internationally, indicators of performance and excellence in research emphasize research quantity and quality, faculty-to-student ratio, international outlook (proportions of international staff and students), and financing (e.g., income from industry) (e.g., World University Rankings; QS University Rankings). The measurement of these indicators is seldom explicitly geared towards responsible research and integrity. In addition, academic reputation is used as an indicator, but rarely with a focus on responsible research culture. Nationally, ministries and national bodies apply a variety of key performance indicators, which may guide RPOs' status and/or funding. Again, responsible research culture and proactive measures are likely not used as performance indicators. In either case, performance indicators risk becoming the primary objective, overshadowing knowledge creation. This tendency could be exacerbated if performance indicators materialize the backwash effect, that is, measurement indicators become the primary objective of activities. From the perspective of responsible research, such a backwash effect could be detrimental if indicators steer the focus to measurable outputs at the expense of the processes of creating research-based knowledge and output.

Research misconduct is not only about “bad apples”; it is influenced by institutional norms, pressures, cultural expectations, and systemic incentives. Quantitative performance metrics and funding competition have negative implications for RI by increasing institutional pressures. Evidence further indicates that performance- and ranking-driven environments discourage researchers, especially early-career researchers, to report RM, especially when recognition systems emphasise outputs over responsible research practices, due to fear of career damage or retaliation.

Stakeholder concerns. Stakeholders emphasize the importance of building institutional culture and the internalization of RE/RI values, including valuing diverse research outputs. An open research culture, in which errors and failures can be discussed in a supportive and non-punitive manner, empowers researchers and other stakeholders to raise concerns and contributes to higher integrity standards across the research system. On the contrary, an environment where researchers face tension between ethics and integrity standards and institutional expectations of efficiency, progress, and growth is not sustainable. Stakeholders highlight the problems with a “publish or perish” culture and emphasize the need to focus on qualitative indicators. They call for making academia a healthier work environment by supporting “slow science” and researchers’ well-being and reducing pressures. RI problems and solutions are connected to institutional research cultures, calling for a culture of responsibility that enables mentoring and reduces pressure. To support such a shift, institutions may consider developing and using indicators that explicitly capture RE/RI, including a culture conducive to RE/RI, such as composite measures of trust, transparency, and psychological safety, including the extent to which researchers feel able to discuss errors and failures without fear of repercussion. Change is a matter of shaping competencies, incentives, communities, and opportunities. Cultivating a culture of integrity becomes increasingly important to strengthen public confidence in scientific research.

2. For the research community to be able to commit to responsible action in research, the prerequisites for responsible action must be in place. Institutions have a primary responsibility to provide the services and infrastructure (such as research integrity services, data management support, and specialised advisory functions) that make responsible research practices feasible and easier to implement in everyday research. This involves the recognition that responsible action may not be the fastest route to end results and may require time and various forms of support. Stakeholders, for example, highlight the tension between “publish or perish” cultures and the time-intensive nature of responsible research, advocating for “slow science” approaches that prioritise quality over speed and quantity. A proactive institutional approach to RE/RI therefore requires recognition of time as a critical resource, including space for reflection, mentoring, and collective learning. It recognises that upholding the highest standards of RE/RI may require effort, time, and other resources. This also requires making guidelines and training materials accessible in various languages. Accessibility of multilingual training materials and the provision of multilingual guidance and procedures are core components of a supportive RI infrastructure that aims to ensure equitable participation across diverse and international research communities.

3. Integrity-related contributions (such as mentoring roles, participation in RE/RI-related committees, other RE/RI-promoting activities that sustain ethical research environments, emotional and care work involved in supporting colleagues and maintaining fair and respectful research environments, particularly for researchers in vulnerable or precarious positions) should be recognized as academic achievements. To truly recognize the work that individuals do for responsible research and for upholding a culture of integrity, RPOs must give greater weight to such activities in assessment processes of individuals, including recruitment. Appraisals must acknowledge these as academic merits alongside research publications, financing obtained, theses supervised, and teaching. This requires a substantial shift in the appraisal of research activities. Some national templates, such as the Finnish National Board on Research Integrity (TENK) researcher CV, already demonstrate how ethics- and integrity-related activities can be formally documented as professional merits.

4. Integrity infrastructures are vulnerable to misuse, such as malicious allegations, including the weaponisation of RI-related procedures to address personal conflicts or normal scientific disagreements, which can have a corroding effect on the culture of integrity and place an unnecessary burden on RI infrastructure. RI ultimately manifests in responsible behaviors and actions, or a lack of these. Creating common understanding through accessibility to information and support while recognizing diversity can help ensure equitable commitment to integrity across the research community. RPOs must ensure that researchers have access to guidelines and expectations, and the opportunity and incentive to align their actions with them, for example by ensuring that guidance is practical, visible, and supported by appropriate institutional incentives. Mechanisms for justified reporting may be weak as institutions may not prioritize addressing research misconduct due to reasons such as reputational risk. Furthermore, stakeholders emphasize the importance of ensuring that every researcher has access to a safe environment for seeking advice and discussing RE/RI issues without fear of retaliation or career damage, including access to trusted advisors without conflicting interests.

5. RE/RI leadership competencies should be consciously developed with attention to the next generation of leaders across all levels of research governance. Research conduct depends, among other things, on the perceived behavior of supervisors and senior researchers, leaders, and majorities. The analysis of national RE/RI surveys indicated that much more attention must be given to leadership and related competencies to build a culture of integrity, particularly in relation to training senior researchers who shape everyday research environments. RE/RI leadership principles highlight that high-quality research requires systemic support and ensures that ethical conduct is not optional or reactive, but foundational and proactive and that effective leaders act not only as administrators but also as moral role models who demonstrate virtues such as fairness, responsibility, and care.

References

- Bernabe, R., Löfström, E., Tammeleht, A., Slesinger, I., Sairio, A., Aryal, P., KHAYADI DASH, K. C., Kaila, E., Coman, A., Mbanya, V., Iordanou, K., Simm, K., & Husum, T. L. (2025). BEYOND Guidelines for Preventing and Addressing Research Misconduct. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17720039>
- Mežinska, S., Lasmane, E., Poļaka, I., & van den Hooff. (2024). Report on the results of the BEYOND public consultation. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13906446>
- Rodrigues, R., & Pizzolato, D. (2023). Policy Brief 1: Addressing the Socio-economic Consequences of Research Misconduct. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10776390>
- Slesinger, I., Dilger, J. Kumar, R., Vinders, J., Rodrigues, R., Simm, K., Zamenska, J., Lang, H., van den Hooff, S., Fanelli, D., Coman, A., Husum, T. L., Tammeleht, A., Löfström, E., Mežinska, S., & Lasmane, E. (2023). Insights from the literature review on behavioural ethics, moral psychology & case-based methodologies and review of real-life case studies of research misconduct. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10617602>
- Tammeleht, A., Antoniou, J., de La C. Bernabe, R., Chapin, C., van den Hooff, S., Mbanya, V. N., Parder M.L., Sairio A., Videnoja K. & Löfström, E. (2025). Manifestations of research ethics and integrity leadership in national surveys – cases of Estonia, Finland, Norway, France and the Netherlands. *Accountability in Research*, 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2025.2481940>
- Uusberg, A., de Vos, M., Andres, S., Voodla, A., Fanelli, D., & Iordanou, K. (2025). Behavioral insights for improving research integrity. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17871646>